

Complexes of Diaryltin Dihalides with 2,2'-Bipyridyl

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The interaction of diaryltin dihalides with 2,2'-bipyridyl yields white crystalline 1 : 1 complexes of the general formula $R_2SnX_2 \cdot bipy$ (R = phenyl, benzyl, *o*-tolyl, *m*-tolyl, or *p*-tolyl; X = Cl, Br, I). The complexes are thermally stable, insoluble in organic solvents and almost insensitive to atmospheric moisture. The infrared spectra of the complexes are discussed.

The increasing interest in the preparation and stereochemistry of 2,2'-bipyridyl complex with alkyltin halides¹⁻⁶ and some corresponding aryltin derivatives⁷ prompted us to synthesise a few new complexes of the type $R_2SnX_2 \cdot bipy$ (R = phenyl, benzyl, *o*-tolyl, *m*-tolyl, or *p*-tolyl; X = Cl, Br, I). The infrared spectra of the complexes have been recorded and the changes in the fundamental absorptions of the ligand on complexation are discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL

The parent diaryltin dihalides were synthesised by the reported methods⁸⁻¹⁰. 2,2'-Bipyridyl of analytical grade (British Drug House) was used without further purification.

Preparation of diaryltin (2,2'-bipyridyl) dihalides : The complexes were prepared by the following method reported earlier for dialkyltin complexes³.

The ethereal solutions of diaryltin dihalides (2 mmole in 20 ml ether) and 2,2'-bipyridyl (2 mmole in 25 ml. ether) were mixed. The precipitated solid was filtered, washed 2-3 times with the solvent and dried under vacuum (yield 80-90%).

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1. D. Blake, G. E. Coates and J. M. Tate, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 756.
2. D. L. Alleston and A. G. Davies, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 2050.
3. T. Tanaka, M. Komura, Y. Kawasaki and R. Okawara, *J. Organometal Chem.*, 1964, **1**, 484.
4. R. J. H. Clark and C. S. Williams, *Spectrochim. Acta.*, 1965, **21**, 1861.
5. R. C. Poller and D. L. B. Toley, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, 1578.
6. R. J. H. Clark, A. G. Davies and R. J. Puddephatt, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 1828.
7. T. N. Srivastava and M. P. Agarwal, (In Press).
8. R. K. Ingham, S. D. Rosenberg and H. Gilman, *Chem. Rev.*, 1960, **60**, 459.
9. J. B. Pedley and H. A. Skinner, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1959, **55**, 544.
10. K. Sisido, Y. Takeda and Z. Kinugawa, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 538.

The complexes are thermally stable and almost insensitive to atmospheric moisture. They are sparingly soluble in polar organic solvents. The complexes on interaction with mercuric chloride yield mercury (2,2'-bipyridyl) dichloride and the parent diaryltin dichloride indicating that mercuric chloride is a better acceptor than diaryltin dichlorides.

DISCUSSION

The analytical data of the compounds are summarised in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Analytical data of diaryltin (2,2'-bipyridyl) dihalide complexes

$R_2SnX_2 \cdot C_{10}H_8N_2$		m.p. ($^{\circ}C$)	Sn(%) Found (Calc)	C(%) Found (Calc)	H(%) Found (Calc)	N(%) found (Calc)
1. $R = C_6H_5$	$X = I$	199	17.1 (17.4)	38.6 (38.7)	2.5 (2.6)	4.4 (4.1)
2. $C_6H_5CH_2$	Cl	141-143 (dec)	23.0 (22.5)	54.5 (54.6)	4.3 (4.2)	5.2 (5.3)
3. <i>o</i> - $C_6H_4CH_3$	Cl	110	22.8 (22.5)	54.8 (54.6)	4.0 (4.2)	5.4 (5.3)
4. <i>o</i> - $C_6H_4CH_3$	Br	252	19.1 (19.3)	46.3 (46.7)	3.8 (3.6)	4.8 (4.5)
5. <i>m</i> - $C_6H_4CH_3$	Cl	259	22.6 (22.5)	54.5 (54.6)	4.4 (4.2)	5.5 (5.3)
6. <i>p</i> - $C_6H_4CH_3$	Cl	218	22.6 (22.5)	54.5 (54.6)	4.0 (4.2)	5.5 (5.3)
7. <i>p</i> - $C_6H_4CH_3$	Br	217	19.2 (19.3)	47.3 (46.7)	3.9 (3.6)	4.6 (4.5)
8. <i>p</i> - $C_6H_4CH_3$	I	176-178	16.6 (16.7)	40.9 (40.5)	3.1 (3.1)	4.0 (3.9)

Infrared Spectra: The infrared spectra of the compounds were recorded as KBr discs using Perkin Elmer Spectrophotometer 337 in the range 4000-400 cm^{-1} . The ligand absorptions undergoing a change on complexation are listed in Table 2.

Ligand absorption bands: The spectra of the complexes show two absorptions of strong intensity located at 1599 ± 11 and 1440 ± 10 cm^{-1} associated with C=C and C=N stretching vibrations. The corresponding absorptions are found to occur at 1580 and 1460 cm^{-1} in the free 2,2'-bipyridyl¹¹. The displacement in the position of these bands is indicative of complexation.

11. A. J. Carty and D. G. Tuck, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 1081.

TABLE 2

Infrared absorption frequencies (cm⁻¹) of R₂SnX₂.bipy

Assignment	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)
C=C and C=N Stretching Vibrations	1595 vs	1595 m	1598 m	1595 s	1600 m	1590 m	1595 vs	1610 m
Pyridine breath- ing mode.	1445 vs	1448 vs, br	1430 vs	1445 vs	1448 vs	1450 vs	1440 vs	1435 vs, br
C-H out-of- plane deformation	1028 vs	1015 m	1010 s	1015 s	1018 vs	1015 m	1018 vs	1030 w
Ligand band	776 vs	770 s	750 vs	790 m	763 vs	762 s	765 vs	760 vs
	745 s	750 vs	739 vs	755 vs	732 s	720 m	723 m	730 s
			722 vs ↑	720 m ↑				720 s ↑
	435 sh	426 w	411 s			430 vw	435 w	430 m

An absorption at 990 cm⁻¹ in the spectrum of 2,2'-bipyridyl, assigned to pyridine breathing mode, shifts to higher frequency and gets intensified on complexation^{1a}. This band has invariably been identified in all diaryltin dihalide complexes at 1020±10 cm⁻¹ and its intensity is found to increase on co-ordination. The band at 760 cm⁻¹ in the free ligand splits and a doublet is observed in the spectra of the complexes. Another band occurring at 404 cm⁻¹ in the uncomplexed ligand also shows a positive shift on co-ordination⁴. The infrared data described above suggest that 2,2'-bipyridyl, a bidentate ligand, forms hexa-co-ordinated octahedral complexes with diaryltin dihalides.

Tin-chlorine Stretching vibrations: The infrared spectra of some of the diaryltin (2,2'-bipyridyl) dichlorides were also recorded in nujol mull in the region 400–200 cm⁻¹ and the asymmetric and symmetric tin-chlorine stretching vibrations have been identified at 252±8 and 228±12 cm⁻¹ respectively. In the parent diaryltin dichlorides, the corresponding absorptions occur at 394 and 336±15 cm⁻¹. The lowering in Sn-Cl stretching absorptions may be due to the increase in the co-ordination number of the tin atom.

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